

NOTES

Heterocyclic Base Adducts of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) Chelates of *o*-Hydroxy Acetophenone

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IN view of extensive work on acetylacetonates and its resemblance with the base adduct formation, adducts of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) chelates of *o*-hydroxy acetophenone with heterocyclic amines are described here.

Experimental

All chemicals used are of AnalaR grade. Absolute ethanolic solutions of metal chlorides were each treated with *o*-hydroxy acetophenone in 1 : 2 proportion followed by dropwise addition of dilute ammonium hydroxide. The precipitated compounds were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum in a desiccator.

To the suspension of aquo adducts so obtained in ethanol, respective nitrogen bases were added in 1 : 2 proportion and the mixtures refluxed for 1 hr. The resulting clear solutions were kept overnight when crystalline compounds of the base adducts appeared. These were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum.

Metals in the complexes were estimated by standard gravimetric or volumetric methods and nitrogen by microanalysis. Conductance was measured using 10^{-3} M acetone solutions of the complexes by Toshniwal conductance bridge. Magnetic measurements were made at 25° over solid specimens by Gouy method. Infrared spectra were recorded using Perkin Elmer 337 and Beckman IR 12 spectrophotometers. Electronic spectra were recorded by Hilger Watt Uvispeck spectrophotometer using 10^{-3} M (acetone-base) solution of the complexes. Analytical data are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes reported here have the formula ML_2B_2 , whereas zinc(II), cadmium(II) and copper(II) complexes have ML_2B , where B is the heterocyclic base and LH is *o*-hydroxy acetophenone. Cobalt(II) complexes are pink, nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes are green while zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes are white.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compounds	m.p. °C	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)	
			Metal	Nitrogen
1. $CoL_2(Q)_2$	165	4.9	9.85 (10.04)	4.25 (4.77)
2. $CoL_2(IQ)_2$	185	5.0	9.81 (10.04)	4.1 (4.77)
3. $CoL_2(\text{Morph})_2$	195	5.2	11.51 (11.72)	5.28 (5.57)
4. $NiL_2(Q)_2$	208	2.9	9.75 (10.00)	4.15 (4.77)
5. $NiL_2(IQ)_2$	205	3.2	9.68 (10.00)	4.21 (4.77)
6. $NiL_2(\text{Morph})_2$	207	3.5	11.35 (11.68)	5.18 (5.57)
7. $CuL_2(Q)$	268	1.75	18.45 (18.73)	2.75 (3.03)
8. $CuL_2(IQ)$	245	1.78	18.56 (18.73)	2.72 (3.03)
9. $CuL_2(\text{Morph})$	260	1.83	14.82 (15.11)	2.81 (3.33)
10. $ZnL_2(Q)$	212	—	18.68 (14.07)	2.71 (3.01)
11. $ZnL_2(IQ)$	175	—	18.74 (14.07)	2.68 (3.01)
12. $ZnL_2(\text{Morph})$	262	—	15.15 (15.48)	3.02 (3.31)
13. $CdL_2(Q)$	185	—	21.35 (21.97)	5.12 (5.47)
14. $CdL_2(IQ)$	205	—	21.23 (21.97)	5.15 (5.47)
15. $CdL_2(\text{Morph})$	215	—	23.15 (23.96)	5.65 (5.96)

Q=Quinoline, IQ=Isoquinoline; Morph=Morpholine.

These have relatively low melting points and are soluble in acetone in which medium the molar conductance values are low indicating non-electrolytic nature of the compounds. Magnetic moment values of cobalt, nickel, and copper complexes are in the range of 4.9-5.2, 2.9-3.5 and 1.75-1.83 B.M., respectively (Table 1). In the infrared spectra of *o*-hydroxy acetophenone $\nu(C=O)$ appears² at 1650 cm^{-1} . In the metal chelates the $\nu(C=O)$ shifts to low frequency region and appears at $\sim 1605\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting³ the bonding through the oxygen atom. In the base adducts the $\nu(C=O)$ shifts slightly to higher frequency region on coordination with nitrogen ligands. In addition to this, most of the absorption bands due to free nitrogen bases are modified in the base adducts indicating their coordination to the metal ions. This has been further substantiated by the observation⁴ of $\nu(M-O)$ and $\nu(M-N)$ at 420-450 and 250-280 cm^{-1} regions, respectively in the far infrared spectra of the complexes.

In the electronic spectra of cobalt complexes two bands are observed at 18.8-19.2 (35-36) and ~ 8.5 (18) kK regions attributable⁴ to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and

${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ transitions, respectively suggestive of a spin free octahedral configuration of these compounds in agreement with the magnetic moment data. Nickel complexes give rise to three absorption bands at 10.0 (4), 15.8 (6) and 28.5 (300) kK regions assignable⁵ to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively indicating an octahedral stereochemistry. In case of copper(II) chelate two bands are observed at 18.0 and 14.8 kK regions whereas in the case of the base adducts only a single band is observed at 15.3-15.5 kK with an increase in the value of the molar absorptivity. The disappearance of the former band, the increase in the intensity and the clear isobestic point confirm that only two species are involved. On the basis of many analogous observations⁶⁻⁷ the copper complexes presumably are penta-coordinated.

On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral studies, zinc and cadmium complexes possibly are penta-coordinated as observed⁸ in the case of base adducts of *bis*-(acetylacetonato)zinc. In view of the spherical symmetry of this ion and in absence of crystal field effects penta-coordination is not quite unusual in these cases.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Benzoyl Glycine by Peroxydisulphate

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KINETICS of oxidation of various organic and inorganic compounds by peroxydisulphate has been reviewed^{1,2}. The kinetic study on the oxida-

tion of some amino acids has been reported by Srivastava and Chandra³. Such a study may help in visualizing the role of amino acid derivatives in biological systems where they are likely to undergo oxidation reactions.

Experimental

Potassium peroxydisulphate (E. Merck, G.R.), benzoylglycine (B.D.H., A.R.), silver nitrate (B.D.H.) and all other chemicals used were of high purity. All the solutions were prepared in distilled water. The reaction at desired temperature was followed by estimating excess of peroxydisulphate by standard iodometric method of Szabo *et al*⁴ as modified by Khulbe and Srivastava⁵.

Product analysis :

Under the kinetic conditions, the final oxidation products of benzoylglycine were benzoic acid, formaldehyde and ammonia. Benzoic acid was detected by spotting the reaction mixture with bromophenol blue which gives yellow brown spot⁶. The aldehyde was characterized by preparing 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative⁷ in the presence of 0.005 M NaOH. Ammonia formed was detected by Nessler's reagent. The low yield of aldehyde indicates that it combines with the ammonia formed during the reaction. For the same reason formaldehyde is detected only in the presence of NaOH, because the latter facilitates the evolution of ammonia.

Results and Discussion

The reaction was found to follow first order rate law with respect to $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ at all concentrations. The velocity constant decreases slightly with increase in $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$, which is attributed to an increase in ionic strength or partly due to the formation of ion pairs⁸ [Table 1(a)]. The specific reaction rate remains almost the same at all concentrations of benzoylglycine, but is linearly related to silver ion concentration [Table 1(b) and (c)].

The salt effect is negative. The specific inhibitory effect of various cations followed the general order $K^+ > Na^+ > Li^+ > H^+$ depending upon charge size ratio⁹.

The reaction was studied at different temperatures ranging from 30 to 45° so as to calculate various energy parameters. The value of energy of activation, frequency factor, entropy of activation were found to be 13.72 k cal mole⁻¹, 1.62×10^6 sec⁻¹ and -41.18 e.u., respectively.

The SO_4^+ radical was detected¹⁰ by allyl acetate and esr spectroscopically. The formation of radicals NH_2-CH_2-COO and $\dot{C}H_2NH_2$ were proved by carrying out the polymerization with acrylonitrile. The white polymeric product analysed by ir spectra was found to contain amino and carboxy carbonyl groups. The generation of the above radicals have already been proved by Chandra and Srivastava³.